

MACHINING OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES - TOOL WEAR AND SURFACE INTEGRITY -

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ABSTRACT

The main problem encountered in the conventional machining of metal matrix composites (MMC) is tool wear, which is caused by the hard and abrasive reinforcements. In order to find suitable materials for cutting tools, several aluminium matrix composites were machined with different tools: cemented carbides, coated cemented carbides, polycrystalline diamond (PCD) and a CVD diamond coating on cemented carbide and on Si_3N_4 ceramics.

Another important factor is the surface integrity of the machined metal matrix composites. Damage to the reinforcements, caused by the machining process, can lead to a decrease in the properties of the components. The surfaces of metal matrix composites, machined by turning and milling, were analysed.

THE USE OF DIFFERENT CUTTING MATERIALS FOR MACHINING ALUMINIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

Comprehensive tests were carried out in order to evaluate a large number of cutting materials (cemented carbides, cutting ceramics, coated cemented carbides, and (PCD)). The suitability of the cutting materials for machining different light metal composites is compared in Fig. 1, whereby the degree of tool wear was taken as the evaluation criterion. The number of suitable cutting materials depends on the hardness of the reinforcement in the composite. Due to the low degree of hardness of the short fibres, all materials are suitable for machining aluminium alloy with $\delta\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ short-fibre reinforcement. A CVD diamond coating as well as PCD and coarse and medium-grained cemented carbides are suitable for the machining of SiC-reinforced aluminium. However, only PCD can be used for machining aluminium reinforced with B_4C particles, because these particles are extremely hard.

POLYCRYSTALLINE DIAMOND

Polycrystalline diamond proved to be well-suited for machining all the aluminium composites tested. Especially as far as aluminium reinforced with B_4C particles is concerned, PCD is the only cutting material with which practice-relevant tool lives are achieved. Due to the dominating role played by PCD in the machining of MMC, comprehensive analyses were performed

with regard to the use of this cutting material in order to determine the influence of the cutting parameters on the wear behaviour. In addition, a variety of modifications with respect to the type of PCD, the cutting edge geometry and the surface treatment of the PCD insert, were examined.

Tool material	AlSi12CuMgNi 20 vol.% δ -Al ₂ O ₃	AlMgSi1Mn 20 vol.% SiC	AlMg3 10 vol.% B ₄ C
cemented carbide coarse-grain	o	o	-
cemented carbide medium-grain	o	o	-
cemented carbide fine-grain	o	-	-
Al ₂ O ₃ -ceramics	o	-	-
Al ₂ O ₃ / TiC-ceramics	o	-	-
AlON-coating	o	-	-
TiN-coating	o	-	-
TiAlN-coating	+	-	-
CVD-diamond- coating	+	+	-
PCD	++	++	++

++: very well-suited; +: well-suited; o: suited; -: unsuited

Figure 1. Comparison of the suitability of different cutting tool materials

The Influence Exerted by the PCD Grain Size

In order to examine the influence of the PCD grain size on tool wear when machining different aluminium composites, turning tests were performed with PCD of medium grain size (PCD-MG) and coarse grain size (PCD-CG) on all composites. In addition to this, a fine-grained PCD (PCD-FG) was used to machine aluminium reinforced with SiC and B₄C particles. The most significant properties of the different types of PCD, as well as the reinforcements in the aluminium matrix composites, are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 3 shows the results of these tests with regard to tool wear. It can be seen that, as far as the machining of aluminium reinforced with δ -Al₂O₃ is concerned, the grain size of the PCD barely influences tool wear. In contrast to this, a distinct reduction in wear with increasing PCD grain size is evident with respect to the machining of materials reinforced with SiC and B₄C particles.

Since PCD is decidedly harder than the reinforcements and the PCD microstructure includes diamond bridging bonds [1], the sliding of the ceramic reinforcements over the effective surface of the PCD cutting edge cannot cause any cutting material abrasion as a result of direct microcutting. Nevertheless, these connecting points between the diamond grains are the weak points of the PCD cutting edge, because the diamond bridging bonds do not completely enclose all the grains, but are only formed in some places, so that pores remain in the PCD composite. The holding forces existing, in addition to the desired diamond bridging bonds, between the PCD components, are attributable to grain encasement by the metallic solvent catalyst. Compared to the covalent bonds between carbon atoms, the metallic bond is less stable under thermal and mechanical load, so that individual diamond grains and groups of grains, which are predominantly metallurgically bonded to the cutting material matrix, are exposed and broken off in the machining process [1].

Figure 2. Properties of the reinforcements and different PCD materials

Figure 3. Tool wear with PCD of different grain sizes when turning reinforced aluminium

The processes which take place directly on the cutting edge are decisive as far as understanding wear mechanisms is concerned. This is where the short fibres or particles come in contact with the rake face. In the course of this, the cutting edge is subjected to high mechanical loads in the area of microcontact with the reinforcement. While only one side of the PCD grains on the rake face and clearance face is not covered by the PCD composite, two sides are unprotected in the area of the cutting edge. Therefore, the grain size ratio of the attacking composite particle and the grain size of the PCD itself, is of particular importance. In the case of fine-grained PCD, the particle coming in contact with the cutting edge is five to six times as big as the PCD grains. This means that, upon impact of the particle, the diamond bridging bonds of one or

more PCD grains are subjected to a very high load, so that the PCD grains can easily break off. In the case of coarse-grained PCD, the PCD grains are twice as big as the attacking composite particles. Consequently, upon impact of the particle, the impact load is mainly absorbed by the PCD grain itself, thus making it more difficult for complete PCD grains to break off. This model allows the results obtained in machining aluminium reinforced with SiC and B₄C to be explained. As opposed to this, the grain size of the PCD is of no significance when machining aluminium with short-fibre δ-Al₂O₃ reinforcement, because the degree of hardness of the δ-Al₂O₃ short fibres is so low in comparison to the PCD composite that the fibres can be cut and, consequently, do not exert such a high load on the PCD cutting edge that PCD particles are directly broken off [2].

The Influence Exerted by the Cutting Speed

Since, when machining composite materials, the dominating wear mechanism is abrasion, the contact path between the cutting edge and the workpiece is of decisive importance as far as the tool wear is concerned. Therefore, the wear values with respect to a constant contact path between cutting edge and workpiece when turning aluminium reinforced with SiC and B₄C particles, are given in Fig. 4. It can be seen that, up to a cutting speed of $v_c = 500$ m/min, almost no increase in wear occurred. A distinct increase in wear can only be determined when the cutting speed is increased to $v_c = 1000$ m/min. It has also been observed that no changes in the wear on PCD cutting edges occurs within a wide cutting speed range up to 500 m/min when drilling and milling aluminium composites [3, 4, 5].

Figure 4. Influence of the cutting speed on the flank wear and the rake face temperature

In order to examine more precisely the influence of the cutting speed on the wear behaviour of cutting edges when machining composite materials, temperature measurements were taken by means of thermoelements arranged in the cutting insert. The cutting surface temperatures are shown as a function of the cutting speed in Fig. 4. It becomes apparent that the cutting surface temperature increases degressively and asymptotically approaches the melting points of the aluminium alloys. When machining material reinforced with B₄C particles, the cutting surface temperatures are higher than the values for SiC-reinforced material. In both cases, when the cutting speed is increased from 500 m/min to 1000 m/min, the cutting surface temperature increases by approx. 100°C. The maximum operation temperature for polycrystalline diamonds

is stated in the literature as being 700°C [6, 7]. The temperatures measured when machining aluminium matrix composites are distinctly below the limit of application for PCD. However, thermally-induced residual stresses are produced by the higher coefficients of thermal expansion of the cobalt than those of diamond in the bonding phase, which weaken the PCD composite [8].

A number of influencing factors are of significance as far as the wear behaviour of PCD when machining MMC is concerned. Firstly, with a cutting speed of $v_c = 1000$ m/min, cutting surface temperatures of almost 600°C are attained, which already weaken the cutting material. In addition, it is to be assumed that distinctly higher temperatures occur when the cutting edge is in direct contact with the reinforcing material of the composite. These so-called "hot spots" have also been observed with respect to friction processes, and appear to an increased degree with higher relative speeds of the contact partner [9,10]. A further important point is that, with increasing cutting speed, the relative speed between the reinforcements and the cutting edge also increases and there is, in particular, a distinct increase in the impact load on the cutting edge.

THE USE OF COATED CEMENTED CARBIDE DRILLS

Due to the high cost of tools when using PCD, particularly of tools with a complex geometry, such as drills or thread drills, efforts must be made to find suitable coatings in this area. The studies carried out with respect to the use of different cutting materials when turning aluminium matrix composites have shown that a TiAlN coating is suitable for machining material reinforced with short fibres, and a CVD diamond coating where there is SiC particle-reinforcement (Fig. 1). In order to also verify these results with regard to drilling, appropriate tests were carried out. The wear curves when machining particle and short fibre-reinforced aluminium with the coated tools are shown in Fig. 5. Uncoated drills were used as reference tools. It can be seen that, in both cases, a considerable reduction in wear is possible as a result of the respective coating.

Figure 5. Tool wear versus drilling distance for uncoated and coated twist drills

THE INFLUENCE ON THE SUBSURFACE ZONE

The cutting and deformation mechanisms of machining affect the surface quality in a multitude of ways. In addition to surface roughness, other characteristics can be influenced, e.g., damage in the form of microcracks and pores, as well as microstructural transformation, plastic deformation, residual stress, and changes in the hardness. As far as the machining of composite materials is concerned, the degree to which the formation of the surface topography will be influenced by the reinforcements and the possible damage which will be caused to the reinforcements in the subsurface zone by the machining, are of particular importance. With reference to these questions, SEM analyses of the machined surfaces were, on the one hand, performed and, on the other hand, cross sections of machined surfaces were prepared, which were examined with the optical microscope for damage to the reinforcements.

Enlargements of segments of the workpiece surfaces of short fibre-reinforced aluminium show that the surfaces exhibit a large number of pores, which primarily develop where individual fibres or groups of fibres are to be found in the boundary layer of the surface. Fig. 6 illustrates this by way of example. Fibre fragments can be clearly recognized in the area of the pore. In addition, the dimensions of the fine grooves in the surface correspond to the dimensions of the fibres and are, therefore, attributable to fibres torn out in this area. In the case of particle-reinforced materials, the workpiece surfaces machined with cemented carbide are also characterized by a large number of pores.

Figure 6. SEM photograph of the turned surface of a reinforced aluminium

In order to analyse the influence of composite materials on the subsurface zone, cross sections of workpiece samples were prepared, which were turned using different cutting parameters. Fig. 7 shows corresponding optical micrographs of subsurface zones which were machined with cemented carbide and different depths of cut. It can be seen that the fibres in cutting direction are subjected to enormous stress by the machining process. As a result of plastic deformations in the subsurface zone, fibres which lie approximately vertical to the surface are deflected and, thus, fractured. The fractures are to be found in an area up to approx. 30 μ m below the surface. Fibres which are oriented at an angle opposite to the cutting direction, as in the middle of Fig. 7, are, on the other hand, cut by the cutting edge and exhibit no other fractures. The same damage to the short fibres is also to be found, parallel to cutting direction, in cross sections of surfaces machined with PCD, however, the fibre fractures are not so pronounced and are limited to a smaller zone, approx. 10 μ m below the surface.

Figure 7. Sections through the turned subsurface zone of reinforced aluminium

Damage, in the form of broken-off particles or particle fragments, is to be found in particle-reinforced aluminium alloys when particles lie directly on the boundary of the surface. In addition, in rare cases, particle fractures can also be found in the subsurface zone.

To summarize, the analyses with respect to the influence on the subsurface zone of aluminium matrix composites have shown that damage to the reinforcements, in the form of fractures, can be caused by the cutting process. The fibre and/or particle fractures are, however, only to be found in a relatively small area approx. 10 - 30 μm below the machined surface. When PCD was used to machine aluminium reinforced with Al_2O_3 short fibres, it was found that distinctly fewer fibre fractures occurred than with cemented carbide. Moreover, pores can develop as a result of particles and/or fibre or particle fragments breaking off the surface. Although damages occurred only in a relative small area below the surface, it is to be assumed that it normally has a negative effect on the properties of aluminium matrix composite components. Therefore, as a matter of principle, the damage caused by machining must be kept to an absolute minimum, which is the reason why the use of PCD tools for processes with geometrically defined cutting edges is to be recommended. This applies, in particular, to final machining processes.

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